

Deliverable 1

Project logo, website and social network accounts

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Version #1

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Introduction

DETEKT is an ACORES2030 project that aims to assess the feasibility of detecting high frequency signals (> 100 Hz) with the Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) technology in a submarine fibre-optic cable between the islands of Faial and São Jorge (Azores archipelago). In the scope of this project and according to its reprogrammed time plan, by the end of December 2025, the Deliverable 1 was produced, i.e., the project logo, website, and social network accounts were created.

Project logo

The idea for the logo was based on the combination of the project name with a fibre-optic submarine cable that continues into a waveform of a click and ends with the shape of a sperm whale (Figure 1). The intention of this idea was to visually summarise the goal of the project: “to detect, on a fibre-optic cable, the click of a sperm whale”.

Figure 1 – Logo of DETEKT project. Designed by Fran Félix Z.

Website

According to the dissemination and communication plan, the DETEKT website (Figure 2; <https://whales.scienceontheweb.net/index.php/projects/detekt>) would encompass a simple and appealing summary of the project goal, by producing a video (Figure 3) and a description of the methodological approach that will be developed (Figure 4). In addition, the website would present the team members and partners (Figure 4). The DETEKT website was done within the Azores Whale Lab (AWL) website, where several other projects of the DETEKT team are presented.

Figure 2 – Section of the DETEKT website. Edited by Rui Prieto.

Figure 3 – Sections of the video produced for the DETEKT website. Edited by Rui Prieto.

Figure 4 – Sections of the methodological approach and the team members of the DETEKT website. Edited by Rui Prieto.

Social network accounts

Similarly, as for the website, within the dissemination and communication plan of the DETEKT project, the idea was to create accounts on Facebook, Instagram and X. However, at the present time, Facebook and X are no longer considered suitable platforms for research projects, so Instagram (Figure 5; <https://www.instagram.com/detekt.2025>) and BlueSky (Figure 5; <https://bsky.app/profile/detekt.bsky.social>) accounts were created, instead. These accounts will be populated with updates on the project development. In addition, the DETEKT website also directs to the project social networks (right side of Figure 2) to increase the visibility of the social networks.

Figure 5 – Profile sections of the DETEKT project Instagram (top) and BlueSky (bottom) social networks.

Conclusion and next steps

As proposed in the approved application and reprogrammed time plan, deliverable 1 was successfully developed (project logo, website and social network accounts were created) and the social networks will be updated, throughout the project, with news and developments. Although this document has only been sent in February 2026, the logo, website and social network accounts were created within the scheduled time plan.

Future steps include obtaining the scientific permit to perform the planned fieldwork, prepare the fieldwork equipment and trips to obtain the sperm whale dataset on playbacks and tagging recordings, and contract another researcher that will support the fieldwork trips and their preparation, process and analyse the data. The fieldwork trips are planned to occur between June and August 2026 and the contract of the researcher is planned to start on May 2026.